

INTENSITIES OF POTATO LATE BLIGHT (*Phytophthora infestans* (Mont) de Bary) AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH BIOPHYSICAL FACTORS IN MAJOR POTATO PRODUCTION DISTRICTS OF AWI ZONE, NORTHWESTERN ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT: Potato is an important food security crop. It is highly attacked by pathogenic fungi, *Phytophthora infestans*, which results in severe yield loss under favorable conditions. A survey of potato late blight disease was carried out in Fagita Lekoma and Banja districts of Awi Zone, Northwestern Ethiopia, to quantify the prevalence and intensities of late blight during the 2019 main cropping season. A semi-structured questionnaire was developed, and potato growers were interviewed. A total of 60 farmer fields were assessed, and a logistic regression model was used to analyze the associations of biophysical factors with late blight intensities. The result indicated that late blight of potato was prevalent in all farmer fields with varying incidence and severity. The mean maximum and minimum disease incidence (100% and 96%), and percent severity index (PSI) (87.50 and 66.66%) were recorded in Banja and Fagita Lekoma district, respectively. Fields with improved variety, fungicide-sprayed fields, altitude <2300 masl, previous crops planted with wheat, intercropping, vegetative growth stage of crop, and May planting reduced mean disease incidence and severity in the surveyed districts. The reduced variable model revealed that lower (<40%) late blight severity was associated with May-planted fields, previous crops with wheat and maize, and intercropping fields. Use of improved/resistant potato varieties, intercropping with cereal crops, potato rotation with non-host crops, early planting, and spraying novel fungicides reduced late blight intensities and could be used for the management of late blight. Further studies are needed on the late blight of potato in different agroecologies.

Keywords: Association, incidence, severity, late blight, variable

INTRODUCTION

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a tuber crop commonly grown in the highlands of Ethiopia. It produces high calories as rice and wheat, and it is considered a high food security crop due to its high yield at low input cost, with a short crop cycle, and harvested when other crops have not been harvested or depleted from the store [1]. With the increasing population of Ethiopia, potatoes are important for employment, daily consumption, and economic gain.

The potential yield of potatoes can reach up to 45t ha⁻¹; however, potato yield in western Amhara is estimated at about 14 t ha⁻¹ [2]. A threefold reduction of potato yield in western Amhara compared to the potential yield is due to several biotic and abiotic factors. Disease, insect pests, weeds, and nematodes are the major biotic factors that limit potato production [3, 4].

Abiotic factors such as the occurrence of natural hazards, inadequate storage, lack of disease-resistant, and quality tubers, and low market prices of potato at harvesting time were important factors that significantly influence potato productivity [5, 1, 6]. Even though the crop is attacked by a number of diseases such as late blight, bacterial wilt, and early blight, the major one is potato late blight in major production areas of Ethiopia. [4]. The disease is common in all potato-growing areas of Ethiopia, and it is the most important and damaging potato disease [7]. It can also attack other solanaceous plants like tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum*), petunias (*Petunia atkinsiana*), and hairy nightshade (*Solanum sarrachoides*) [8]. Late blight infects all parts of potatoes at any stage of development, and has the potential to destroy potato fields within a few days [9]. Due to late blight infection potato yield loss is estimated about 29-56.95% [10] at Haramaya, 11.4-47.1% at Shewarobit [11], 10.26 to 34.66% at Fagita Lekoma [12] depending on the varieties, and fungicides used. Different types of management options have been developed, and used throughout the world. It can be managed through cultural practices (removal of volunteer potato, intercropping), the use of resistant varieties [42], fungicide applications [36, 43], and integrated late blight disease management [13, 14, 15, 12]. In Northwestern Ethiopia, the disease is severe in the main cropping season (June-September) as a result of the prevalence of favorable weather conditions mainly temperature, rainfall, and relative humidity.

Despite its widespread impact, detailed studies on the spatial distribution and intensity of late blight across districts and *Kebeles* remain limited. In addition, understanding the prevalence and intensity of potato late blight is essential for designing effective integrated management strategies. Hence, the aim of this study was to assess the prevalence, incidence, and severity of late blight disease, and its association with biophysical factors.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Description of the survey area

A survey of potato late blight was carried out during the 2019 main cropping season in the two districts of potato growing areas of Awi administrative zone, namely: Fagita Lekoma and Banja districts (Fig. 1). Fagita Lekoma district is 17 km from Injibara to the north, which is the center town of the Awi Administrative zone, and 105 km from the regional Administrative city of Bahir Dar to the south. It is located 10°57'23" to 11°11'21" North latitude, and 36°40'01" to 37°05'21" longitude, and the elevation ranges from 1800 to 2900 meters above sea level. The mean annual temperature ranges from 9.4°C and 25°C, and the mean rainfall is 2434.6mm [16]. The agroecology of the district is 16% highland and 84% midland. A mixed farming system is commonly practiced in the district. The major crops produced in the district in order of area coverage include wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), maize (*Zea mays*), and *Tef* (*Eragrostis tef*).

Banja district is 122 km from the regional Administrative city of Bahir Dar to the south. The district is the center of town, where Kossober is located. The elevation of Banja lies between 1870 and 3300 meters above sea level. It is located 10°57'17" to 11°03'05" North latitude, and 36°39'09" to 36°48'25" East longitude. The minimum and maximum temperatures are 9.4°C and 26°C. The mean annual rainfall is 2300 mm from June to September. The agroecology is Sub-humid or 80% highland, and 20% midland. The major crops produced in the district in order of area coverage include potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), *Tef* (*Eragrostis tef*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), and maize (*Zea mays*) [17].

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area (GIS map of Ethiopia, 2020)

Table 1. Total rainfall (mm), mean minimum and maximum temperature (° c) of the surveyed districts, during the 2019 main cropping season

District	Parameters	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
Fagita Lekoma	Rainfall	161.4	275.8	235.5	35.5	29.6
	Max T	22.1	21.1	20.9	20.5	21.6
	Min T	11.1	11.6	14.8	14.9	14.9
Banja	Rainfall	215.3	329.7	361.7	374.3	372.7
	Max T	26	23.8	21.4	21.6	21.8
	Min T	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.3	8.9

Source: Western Amhara Meteorology Agency, 2019
Max T maximum temperature and Min T minimum temperature

Sample unit and disease assessment

Two districts (Fagita Lekoma and Banja) were considered for the survey. The two districts were selected based on potato production, and coverage, disease problem, and in discussion with the district extension workers and agricultural development agents.

In each district five *Kebele* administrations (*KAs*) [lower administrative unit] were selected based on disease problems, and potato production (Fig. 1). In each *Kebele* administration, six potato-growing farmer fields were selected randomly. Totally 60 farmer fields in the two districts were assessed. In each sample field, quadrates (1m x 1m) were sampled by moving diagonally across each field from one end to the other in an ‘X’ pattern.

The prevalence of disease was calculated by using the number of fields affected divided by the total number of fields assessed, and expressed in percentage. Disease incidence of potato late blight was assessed by visual examination, and counting of stands with the disease on the leaves symptom of potato plants and calculated using the formula Eqn. 1.

$$\text{Disease incidence (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of plants infected by disease}}{\text{Total number of plants assessed}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 1

The data on disease severity was recorded using a 1-9 rating scale of Shutong et al. [18]. The severity was calculated using the formula by Wheeler [19] as Eqn. 2.

$$\text{PSI} = \frac{\text{SNR}}{\text{NPR} \times \text{MSS}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 2

PSI = Percent severity index; SNR = Sum of numerical ratings; NPR = Number of plants rated; MSS = Maximum score in the scale.

Biological and physical factors like the previous crops, cropping system, the variety grown, planting time, crop growth stage, and altitude were recorded. The previous crop, fungicide sprayed or not, variety grown, and planting time was recorded by interviewing the farmer, while the cropping system (sole, and intercropped), and growth stage were recorded by visual

observation in the field. The altitude in the surveyed fields was recorded using GPS and classified into ≥ 2300 , and < 2300 meter above sea level.

Statistical data analysis

The collected survey data were analyzed using SPSS software version 25 and descriptive statistics was used to summarize the data. The incidence and severity of late blight disease was grouped in to two binary dependent variable on the bases of overall approximate mean value of incidence (60%) and severity (40%). Class boundaries of < 60 and $\geq 60\%$ for incidence and < 40 and ≥ 40 for severity data was considered for analysis. Disease intensity contingency table by independent variable and bivariate distribution of fields was constructed (Table 4).

Logistic regression model was used to analyze the associations of late blight intensities with the different variable classes in SAS procedure of the GENMOD [20]. Dependent variables (late blight intensities) associations with independent variables were tested first in a single variable model. Then, independent variables which showed significant associations with disease incidence and severity were added to a reduced multiple variable models [21].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmers practice for potato production

Intercropping potatoes with other crops such as maize, faba bean, barley, and wheat is widely practiced in both districts of Fagita Lekoma, and Banja. Semagn et al. [22] reported that intercropping potatoes with maize, faba bean, field pea, brassica, linseed, and wheat is common in Ethiopia. In addition, beans, barley, and wheat are grown in potato fields after flowering and maturity but before harvest. In the main season production (May to September), farmers harvest tubers from half of the total area cultivated only for consumption. The remaining half of potato cultivated area were left in the soil without harvesting tubers and harvest later when irrigation time is approaching and replant again (their own seed source) in irrigation time (dry seasons mainly January and February) in well prepared or ploughed soil in rows. In the soil (without harvesting), tubers stay without sprouting and degeneration from September to January in well drained soils in the survey area. This helps farmers not only to save tubers in the soil but also to get additional yields from the intercrop, and reduce losses due to late blight. In addition, the practice reduces the need to buy or use commercial fertilizers because the leaves of potato fall, and are used as a soil nutrient. This is a common practice in the surveyed districts in which the majority of the farmers have a small and fragmented landholding system.

The improved potato varieties widely grown in the surveyed districts are Belete, Gudene, Guassa, and Zengena while local varieties *Key*, *Abalo*, and *Samune* are grown in the surveyed districts of Awi Administrative zone (Table 3). Semagn et al. [22] reported the farmer variety *Abalo*, *Samune*, *Key*, and *Siquare* are grown in the cool highlands of the Amhara region (Lai-Gaint, Banja, Quarit, and Yilmana districts) while *Agazer*, and *Nech Ababa* are the two local varieties largely grown in Shashemene. *Key denich* was the dominant local variety grown in the surveyed areas. This may be due to farmers prefer this variety because of its taste, take short time in cooking, and durability for storage in the soil (without harvest). Farmers also used left harvesting potato in the soil until the next season of planting, and used as seed sources. In addition, potato harvesting was done after the harvest of the component crop in intercropped, and rely cropping systems. Improved potato varieties were grown mainly for market value, and distributed to neighbor farmers, and as seed sources for next season production due to limited

access, and the high price of these varieties. Agegnehu et al. [23] reported that improved varieties are not commonly found in the hands of farmers. Now, a day's farmers shift to the cultivation of *Acacia decurrens* plantation. This plantation plays a significant role in the improvement of soil fertility [16]. In addition, *Acacia decurrens* is ideal for the rehabilitation of degraded land, climate resilience, the elimination of weeds, and is a major source of income in the surveyed districts. Farmers practiced planting *Acacia decurrens* in combination with small cereal crops (mainly *Tef*, wheat, and barley) in the first year, and only harvested the crop at maturity while leaving the *decurrens*. In the second year, the plant grows up with grasses for animal feed. Finally, the plants at the recommended age (forest) were sold to merchants through brokers for charcoal production, and then the charcoal was transported to Addis Ababa, Mekelle, and Sudan. The first two cities listed above were the main destination areas for charcoal. Several thousands of people (both sex) were served for collecting, and preparation of raw materials (sand soil, forest soil, and compost) for compost, pot filling, raising seedlings in beds in small nurseries, daily watering of seedlings, transporting seedlings to farm, and planting, cutting trees at the base at maturity, and then to small pieces (0.5m), charcoal production, brokers, transportation of charcoal in sacks to roadsides, and load to cars in groups. However, most farmers, especially those who have no cultivated land, are appealing for this practice due to the reduction of crop production, shading effect, takes a lot of time to mature (4-6 years depending on soil fertility level, and vigor of seedlings), and imbalance of sales for the tree, and costs for household needs such as food.

Moreover, summer season production was also shifted to spring season, and irrigation production due to the impact of late blight on potatoes during *Meher* season production. Severe late blight infection in the *Meher* season forced farmers to limit their potato production to the dry season [24, 25]. Smallholder farmers have small land, low access, and high prices of seed tubers of improved potato varieties reducing potato production in the surveyed districts. Furthermore, the prevalence of diseases such as late blight, and bacterial wilt, and insect pests (potato tuber moth) are the major challenges of potato production in the districts. Yazie et al. [26] also reported that disease, insects, storage (decay/sprouted), and marketing (price drop after harvest) are major challenges in Awi zone, East Gojjam, and South Gonder.

Characteristic features of the surveyed fields

Among the varieties grown in the survey fields around 41.67% of potato fields were improved varieties (Belete, Gudene, Guassa and Zengena) while the remaining 58.33% of the potato fields were widely cultivated local varieties (Table 3). Farmers use local potato varieties starting from a long period of time, and local potato variety is the dominant variety grown in North Western Ethiopia [23, 26].

Out of the total surveyed 60 potato fields, 58.43% of them were sole cropped, while 41.57% had been intercropped with wheat, barley, maize, and fababean (Table 3). The fungicides commonly used during the survey were Ridomil Gold 68%WG (Metalaxyl 4% + Mancozeb 64%), Mancozeb 80% WP, and Victory 72% (Metalaxyl 8% + Mancozeb 64%). In the surveyed areas 26.67% and 53.33% of the interviewed farmers used fungicides at Banja, and Fagita Lekoma districts, respectively. On the other hand, (73.33%) at Banja, and 46.67% at Fagita Lekoma districts were not using fungicides. During the survey, 36.67% of potato fields were at vegetative and 63.33% at flowering stages. About 65% of potato fields were sown in the month of May, while 35% were sown in June. But the previous experience of farmers (10 years ago) for planting potato was starting from the first week of April. Planting in the month of May, and June for the current season is due to the late starting of rainfall. Of the surveyed field eight fields

(13.34%) were planted with solanaceous crops (potato) in the previous year while 52 fields (86.66%) were planted with cereal crops (Table 3). Potato is commonly rotated with barley, wheat, faba bean, maize, and *Tef* fields [26].

Late blight prevalence

From the total surveyed fields, 70.39% of the fields were infested with potato late blight disease. Late blight of potatoes was prevalent in both districts surveyed, with a minimum of 61.78% at Fagita Lekoma and a maximum 79% at Banja, respectively (Table 2). Lower temperatures and higher rainfall were recorded at Banja during the survey seasons (Table 1). These conditions are often favorable weather factors for late blight epidemics. Similarly, Kankwatsa et al. [27] reported the heaviest rainfall, and cool weather conditions favored rapid late blight development. Late blight prevalence to varying extents in conditions of higher humidity, low night temperature, and minimal rainfall or heavy dew, and in fields previously sown with solanaceous crops has also been reported [28].

Table 2. Mean, minimum, and maximum prevalence, incidence, and percent severity index (PSI) of late blight in the surveyed areas during the 2019 main cropping season

District	Kebele	N	Prevalence (%)			Incidence (%)			PSI (%)		
			Min	Max	Mean±SD	Min	Max	Mean±SD	Min	Max	Mean±SD
Fagita	Fagita	6	0.00	100	50.83±48.00	0.00	90.00	48.46±42.88	0.00	66.66	24.57±28.78
Lekoma	Sigla dawuna	6	0.00	100	69.44±40.02	0.00	94.44	56.87±44.75	0.00	53.70	22.04±22.96
	Furi jegola	6	0.00	100	56.66±46.33	0.00	85.00	41.45±39.25	0.00	66.66	22.76±24.53
	Gafera	6	0.00	100	49.16±49.17	0.00	81.40	44.28±38.47	0.00	46.60	21.84±20.70
	Chiguali	6	50.00	100	82.77±21.13	25.45	96.00	64.25±26.75	16.34	96.00	64.25±66.66
	Mean		0.00	100	61.78±41.04	0.00	96.00	51.07±36.33	0.00	66.66	25.56±23.07
Banja	Asem selase	6	75.00	100	92.50±11.72	75.60	100	87.02±10.45	40.00	84.40	62.04±16.53
	Gomerta	6	80.00	100	96.66±45.87	66.66	100	83.25±37.37	30.00	87.50	52.67±26.23
	Gagasta	6	0.000	100	75.00±41.83	0.00	100	65.69±37.81	0.00	79.52	39.86±28.04
	Akena	6	0.000	100	76.66±8.16	0.00	100	71.96±12.86	0.00	80.27	29.77±23.53
	Dangia	6	0.000	100	54.16±38.81	0.00	82.50	67.00±37.31	0.00	60.40	27.12±29.77
	Mean		0.000	100	79.00±34.55	0.00	100	70.64±31.65	0.00	87.50	45.71±26.34
Grand Mean			0.000	100	70.39±38.60	0.00	100	60.85±35.19	0.00	87.50	35.64±26.56

N number of potato fields, *Min* minimum, *Max* maximum, *SD* standard error, *PSI* percent severity index

Late blight incidence

The mean incidence of late blight of potato was prevalent in both districts surveyed with varying degrees of incidence. The higher (70.63%) mean incidence at Banja, and the lower (51.06%) mean incidence were recorded at Fagita Lekoma (Table 3). Similarly, the maximum disease incidence of 100% was recorded from Banja district, and the maximum disease incidence of 96% was recorded from Fagita Lekoma district (Table 2). Variations in incidence between locations might be due to differences in environmental factors [29]. Late blight epidemics are severe only when weather conditions are suitable [27]. The mean disease incidence for both districts was 60.85% (Table 2).

Among the *Kebele* Administrations (*KAs*), the highest mean disease incidence was recorded at Asem selase (87.02%) followed by Gomerta (83.25%), and Akena (71.96%), whereas the lowest disease incidence was recorded in Furi jegola (41.45%), followed by Gafera (44.28%), and Fagita (48.46%). Other *KAs* were recorded in the ranges of 56.87-67% mean disease incidence (Table 2). The highest late blight mean disease incidence of (80.45, 64.32, and 70.92%) were recorded from potato fields planted previously with potatoes, in the month of June, and the altitudinal range of ≥ 2300 meters above sea level, respectively. While the lowest

mean incidence (41.0, 58.98, and 37.35%) were recorded from fields previously with *Tef*, May planted, and the altitudinal range of <2300 meters above sea level, respectively (Table 3). The result is primarily attributed to the delay in the onset of the disease on early-planted potatoes. On the other hand, the highest mean disease incidence (85.38%) was recorded from fungicide unsprayed fields when compared with fungicide sprayed fields recorded the lowest (24.05%) incidence. Fungicide application reduced disease incidence, and severity [30]. Beka and Pichiah [31] reported at high altitudes with high precipitations resulting in a conducive environment to boost late blight development.

Potato intercropped with cereal crops such as maize, barley, and wheat had the lowest (50.16%) mean incidence of late blight was recorded. On the other hand, the highest (68.48%) mean incidence was recorded from potato planted as sole cropping system. The highest (80.45%) mean incidence of late blight was recorded from fields planted with solanaceous (potato) crops in the preceding year (Table 3). High levels of disease in these fields may be due to the monoculture of solanaceous crops and the presence of favorable temperatures, and rainfall during the cropping season. Bekele and Eshetu [24] explained that when the environmental conditions become conducive the disease can spread rapidly, and might have the potential to destroy the potato fields completely within three weeks. The highest (80.82 and 66.72%) mean incidence was observed when fields were planted with *the Key variety*, and at the flowering stage, whereas the lowest (13.49 and 47.93%) incidence was observed when fields were planted with *the Belete variety*, and at the vegetative stage, respectively (Table 3). Disease incidence depends on meteorological conditions, potato variety susceptibility to late blight, and the growth stage of the potato during disease attack [29]. Incidence of late blight has been observed in the assessed fields is because of easily spread of the disease mainly by wind and infected tubers. The spores can be dispersed by wind or water and enable the distribution of *P. infestans* to other potato fields [32].

Late blight severity

The overall mean disease severity for both districts was 35.64% (Table 2). The highest mean disease severity was obtained at Banja district while the lowest mean disease severity was obtained at Fagita Lekoma district (Table 3). This is due to the variation in environmental conditions of the surveyed districts; there was higher rainfall, and lower temperature availability in Banja district than Fagita Lekoma district (Table 1). These conditions are ideal for late blight development. Ahmed et al. [33] reported that a significant correlation was found between late blight disease severity, and weather conditions in which 12-24°C temperature range is favorable for the disease. Majid et al. [34] also reported cloudiness or heavy wetness following lower temperature favors disease development.

Among the *KAs*, the highest mean disease severity was recorded in *Kebele Chiguali* (64.25%) followed by *Kebele Asem selase* (62.04%) and *Kebele Gomerta* (52.67%) whereas, the lowest disease severity was recorded in *Kebele Gafera* (21.84%), followed by *Kebele Furi jegola* (22.76%), and *Kebele Sigla dawuna* (22.04%), respectively. Other *Kebeles* were recorded in the range of 24.57-39.86% mean disease severity (Table 2). Disease severity of late blight on potatoes in different locations was recorded in the range of 27.9 to 81.6% [35], and 3.50 to 48.35% [36].

The mean disease severities obtained at different independent variables viz: altitude, planting date, varieties, preceding crops, cropping system, crop growth stage, and fungicide were varied in the surveyed areas. Among these the mean maximum disease severities of 52.59, 50.18, 50.15, 44.66, 41.75, 38.82, and 36.66% were obtained from unsprayed fields, previous crop with potato,

local cultivars, altitude ≥ 2300 meters above sea level, sole cropping, flowering growth stage, and at June planted, respectively in the surveyed districts. The lowest mean severity of 6.24, 10.19, 14.56, 17.49, 27.07, 29.72, and 35.08% were recorded from Belete variety, fungicide sprayed fields, altitude < 2300 meters above sea level, previous crops planted with *Tef*, intercropping, vegetative growth stage, and at May planted, respectively in the surveyed districts (Table 3). In the present study, early planting of potato exhibited low disease severity could be due to environmental conditions that did not co-exist for the infection of late blight. Early planting at the time of rainfall onset contributed to the delay in disease development [27] and the severity is mainly attributed to the susceptibility, and resistance of various varieties grown in many areas, different planting dates (disease escape), and various late blight management practices [3, 37]. Arora et al. [38] reported that a change in the pathogen population toward increased specific virulence, breakdown of disease resistant varieties, and development of resistance to fungicides lead increasing of late blight severity.

Potato intercropped with none host crops reduces the development of the disease. The result of the current study coincides with the findings of Phillips et al. [39] who stated that if diversity is available for plant resistance against late blight, the disease severity would be reduced if any given mixture or variety is grown. *Phytophthora infestans* spread mainly by wind, and rain, the intercrop physically interfere reducing inoculum by entrap the spores [40, 41]. Garlic, faba bean, and barley intercropped with potato showed lower disease severity compared to monoculture potato plants [41]. Generally, late blight severity is reduced in intercropping, early planting, improved potato varieties and fungicide applications at Fagita Lekoma and Banja districts.

Table 3. Mean incidence and percent severity index (PSI) of potato late blight for different independent variables in the surveyed districts during the 2019 main cropping season

Variable	Variable class	N	P	Disease incidence (%)			PSI (%)		
				Min	Max	Mean \pm SD	Min	Max	Mean \pm SD
District	Fagita Lekoma	30	50	0.00	96.00	51.06 \pm 36.33	0.00	66.66	25.57 \pm 23.07
	Banja	30	50	0.00	100	70.63 \pm 31.65	0.00	87.50	45.71 \pm 26.33
Altitude ^a	<2300	18	30	0.00	90.00	37.35 \pm 36.42	0.00	66.66	14.56 \pm 17.83
	≥ 2300	42	70	0.00	100	70.92 \pm 29.76	0.00	87.50	44.66 \pm 24.60
Planting Date	May	39	65	0.00	100	58.98 \pm 38.21	0.00	87.50	35.08 \pm 27.75
	June	21	35	0.00	96.00	64.32 \pm 29.39	0.00	74.67	36.66 \pm 24.75
Variety	Belete	8	13.33	0.00	82.50	13.49 \pm 29.27	0.00	33.33	6.24 \pm 12.39
	Gudene	10	16.67	0.00	81.40	41.57 \pm 33.95	0.00	55.78	20.04 \pm 19.01
	Zengena	3	5.01	0.00	86.54	51.51 \pm 13.05	0.00	60.24	20.96 \pm 4.60
	Guassa	4	6.66	0.00	82.50	46.63 \pm 34.72	0.00	55.00	25.23 \pm 22.93
	Key	22	36.75	0.00	100	80.82 \pm 21.40	0.00	87.50	50.15 \pm 23.83
	Abalo	13	21.58	0.00	100	77.56 \pm 25.80	0.00	80.27	47.73 \pm 23.80
Previous crop	Barley	5	8.33	0.00	100	70.75 \pm 40.13	0.00	75.50	48.57 \pm 28.76
	Wheat	6	10.00	0.00	96.00	63.57 \pm 40.52	0.00	66.00	29.15 \pm 26.03
	<i>Tef</i>	15	25.00	0.00	90.00	41.00 \pm 33.84	0.00	50.00	17.49 \pm 16.10
	Maize	26	43.33	0.00	100	63.74 \pm 31.38	0.00	80.27	37.56 \pm 24.00
	Potato	8	13.34	0.00	100	80.45 \pm 33.86	0.00	87.50	50.18 \pm 29.20
Cropping systems ^b	Intercropping	25	41.67	0.00	100	50.16 \pm 35.78	0.00	79.52	27.07 \pm 25.06
	Sole cropping	35	58.33	0.00	100	68.48 \pm 33.67	0.00	87.50	41.75 \pm 26.64
Growth stage	Vegetative	22	36.67	0.00	100	49.94 \pm 42.71	0.00	87.50	29.72 \pm 29.71
	Flowering	38	63.33	0.00	100	66.72 \pm 29.35	0.00	84.40	38.82 \pm 24.46
Fungicide	Sprayed	24	40	0.00	66.66	24.05 \pm 26.35	0.00	32.00	10.19 \pm 11.29
	Unsprayed	36	60	70.0	100	85.38 \pm 9.16	12.20	87.50	52.59 \pm 19.13

N number of potato fields, P percent, Min minimum, Max maximum, SD standard error, PSI percent severity index, ^aAltitudinally, areas with ≥ 2300 < 2300 m a.s.l. are classified as highland and mid-highland in Ethiopia, respectively, ^bInter refers to fields with potato plus wheat, barley, maize, and faba bean

Association of biophysical factors with late blight incidence and severity

Table 5 presents the associations of various factors with the incidence and severity of potato late blight. A significant association was observed between biophysical factors and late blight incidence and severity. All independent variables were significantly associated with late blight incidence when entered first and last into the model (Table 5). Independent variables such as district, Kebeles, planting date, potato variety used, previous crop, cropping system, crop growth stage, and fungicide used were significantly associated with late blight severity when entered first and last into the model. Planting date ($\chi^2 = 0.40$ and 12.05 , 1 df) showed non-significant and significant associations with late blight severity when entered first and last into the model, respectively (Table 5). The independent variable altitude ($\chi^2 = 1.65$, 1 df) did not show a significant association with late blight severity and was not added to the reduced multiple-variable model.

Table 4. Disease incidence and severity contingency table by independent variable used in regression analysis during the 2019 main cropping season

Variable	Variable class	No- of fields	LB incidence (%)		LB severity (%)	
			<60	≥60	<40	≥40
District	Fagita lekoma	30	16	14	21	9
	Banja	30	6	24	12	18
Kebeles	Fagita	6	3	3	4	2
	Sigla dawuna	6	2	4	4	2
	Furi jegola	6	5	1	5	1
	Gafera	6	2	4	4	2
	Chiguali	6	3	3	4	2
	Asem selase	6	-	6	1	5
	Dangia	6	3	3	4	2
	Gagasta	6	2	4	3	3
	Gomerta	6	-	5	2	4
	Akena	6	1	5	3	3
	Altitude	<2300	18	13	5	16
≥2300		42	9	33	17	25
Planting date	May	39	15	24	21	18
	June	21	7	14	12	9
Variety	Key	22	2	20	7	15
	Abalo	13	2	11	3	10
	Zerngena	3	2	1	3	-
	Guassa	4	3	1	3	1
	Gudene	10	6	4	8	2
	Belete	8	7	1	8	0
Previous crop	Potato	8	1	7	2	6
	Maize	26	8	14	12	14
	Tef	15	9	6	14	1
	Wheat	6	2	4	4	2
	Barley	5	1	4	0	5
Cropping system	Intercropping	25	13	12	18	7
	Sole cropping	35	19	26	15	20
Growth stage	Flowering	38	12	26	18	20
	Vegetative	22	15	7	15	7
Fungicide used	Unsprayed	36	0	36	8	28
	Sprayed	24	22	2	24	0

No- number, LB late blight

Table 5. Logistic regression analysis and likelihood ratio test for independent variables entered first and last in to the model

IV	DF	LB incidence LRT				LB severity LRT			
		Type 1 analysis		Type 3 analysis		Type 1 analysis		Type 3 analysis	
		DR	Pr>x ²	DR	Pr>x ²	DR	Pr>x ²	DR	Pr>x ²
District	1	243.15	<0.0001	0.00	<0.0001	268.17	<0.0001	0.00	<0.0001
<i>Kebeles</i>	9	402.04	<0.0001	134.66	<0.0006	219.30	<0.0001	87.29	<0.0001
Altitude	1	587.69	<0.0001	1.33	<0.0001	312.81	<0.0001	1.65	0.1994
Planting date	1	12.73	<0.0004	61.95	<0.0001	0.40	0.5258	12.05	<0.0005
Variety	5	1006.51	<0.0001	281.86	<0.0001	492.94	<0.0001	92.05	<0.0001
Previous crop	4	49.98	<0.0001	36.88	<0.0001	119.82	<0.0001	48.89	<0.0001
Cropping system	1	8.18	<0.0042	42.05	<0.0003	0.98	0.3219	6.77	<0.0093
Growth stage	1	0.57	0.4516	13.14	<0.0001	1.41	0.2346	19.65	<0.0001
Fungicide used	1	747.53	<0.0001	747.53	<0.0001	297.29	<0.0001	297.29	<0.0001

IN independent variables, DF degree of freedom, LB late blight, LRT likelihood ratio test, DR deviance reduction, Pr probability, χ^2 Chi-Square

All independent variables were tested in the reduced multiple variable model for late blight incidence. Variables such as district, *Kebeles*, planting date, variety, previous crop, cropping system, crop growth stage, and fungicide used were tested in the reduced multiple variable model for late blight severity. The results indicated that the highest late blight incidence was highly associated with Fagita lekoma district, Gagasta, Gomerta and Furi jegola *Kebeles*, altitude ≥ 2300 mean above sea level, all potato varieties, previous crop with potato and *Tef*, flowering growth stage and fungicide unsprayed fields compared to the reference group of each variable (Table 6). On the other hand, lowest late blight incidence was highly associated with Dangia, Gafera, and Fagita *Kebeles*, May planted, and intercropped fields. Late blight severity was highly associated with the variable classes of Furi jegola and Gagasta *Kebeles*, *Key*, *Abalo*, Zengena, Guassa, Gudene, and Belete varieties, previous crop with potato, flowering growth stage, and unsprayed fields compared the reference group of each variable. These independent variables significantly contributed to the severity of late blight on potato fields assessed. The lowest late blight severity was highly associated with Sigla dawuna and Gafera *Kebeles*, previously wheat planted fields (Table 7). In the reduced multiple variable model, Fagita lekoma district, Furi jegola, Gagasta, and Gomerta *Kebeles*, *Key* and *Abalo* potato varieties, previous crop with potato, flowering growth stage, and fungicide unsprayed fields had 1.5092, 1.0724, 2.1278, 1.4882, 5.7465, 4.5426, 1.1474, 1.4912, and 19.0449 times higher probabilities of association with late blight incidence compared to the reference group (Table 6). The variables Fagita, Gafera, and Dangia *Kebeles*, May planted fields, previous crop with wheat and maize, intercropping fields had 0.50, 0.35, 0.31, 0.49, 0.56, 0.83, and 0.47 times lower probabilities of association with late blight incidence compared to the reference group (Table 6). Regarding late blight severity, Furi jegola and Gagasta *Kebeles*, previous crop with potato, flowering growth stage, variables, and unsprayed fields had 1.0523, 1.4765, 1.3599, 1.4993, and 6.6240 times higher probabilities of associations with high (>40%) late blight severity than the reference group (Table 7). Sigla dawuna, and Gafera *Kebeles*, May planted fields, previous crop with maize, wheat, and *Tef* fields had 0.37, 0.46, 0.73, 0.93, 0.49, and 0.75 times lower probability of association with low (<40%) late blight severity than the reference group, respectively (Table 7). Lower association of late blight severity with early planting (May), intercropping, previous crop with wheat and *Tef* suggests the reduction of incidence and severity and could be an option for the management of late blight in the surveyed districts of Fagita Lekoma and Banja.

Table 6. Analysis of deviance, natural logarithms of odds ratio, and standard error of potato late blight incidence on added variables in a reduced model

Independent Variables	DF	LRT		Variable class	Estimate (OR)	Loge	SE	Odds ratio
		DR	Pr> χ^2					
Intercept		75.64	<.0001		-2.3104		0.2656	
District	1	3.92	0.0478	Fagita lekoma	0.4116		0.2080	1.5092
				Banja	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Kebeles	9	11.00	0.0009	Fagita	-0.6923		0.2087	0.5004
		6.65	0.0099	Sigla dawuna	-0.5467		0.2119	0.5788
		0.12	0.7261	Furi jegola	0.0699		0.1997	1.0724
		26.63	<.0001	Gafera	-1.0545		0.2044	0.3484
				Chiguali	0*		0.0000	1.0000
		0.11	0.7395	Asem selase	-0.0669		0.2012	0.9353
		29.92	<.0001	Dangia	-1.1644		0.2129	0.3121
		15.75	<.0001	Gagasta	0.7551		0.1903	2.1278
		3.81	0.0510	Gomerta	0.3976		0.2038	1.4882
				Akena	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Altitude	1	1.32	0.2506	≥ 2300	0.1867		0.1625	1.2053
				< 2300	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Planting date	1	61.08	<.0001	May	-0.7173		0.0918	0.4881
				June	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Variety	5	97.27	<.0001	Key	1.7486		0.1773	5.7465
		67.70	<.0001	Abalo	1.5135		0.1840	4.5426
		212.13	<.0001	Zengena	3.5285		0.2423	34.0728
		62.08	<.0001	Guassa	1.7687		0.2245	5.8632
		40.19	<.0001	Gudene	1.105		0.1714	3.0192
		Belete	0*		0.0000	1.0000		
Previous crop	4	0.45	0.5030	Potato	0.1375		0.2053	1.1474
		1.18	0.2769	Maize	-0.1839		0.1691	0.8320
		8.08	0.0045	Tef	0.5423		0.1908	1.7199
		5.77	0.0163	Wheat	-0.5734		0.2387	0.5636
				Barley	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Cropping system	1	41.43	<.0001	Intercropping	-0.7481		0.1162	0.4733
				Sole cropping	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Growth stage	1	13.08	0.0003	Flowering	0.3996		0.1105	1.4912
				Vegetative	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Fungicide used	1	614.38	<.0001	Unsprayed	2.9468		0.1189	19.0449
				Sprayed	0*		0.0000	1.0000

DF degrees of freedom, DR deviance reduction, LRT likelihood ratio test, Pr probability of a value χ^2 exceeding the deviance reduction, χ^2 chi-square value, *Reference group, OR odds ratio (Exponentiation of the estimates), SE standard error

Table 7. Analysis of deviance, natural logarithms of odds ratio, and standard error of potato late blight severity on added variables in a reduced model

Independent Variables	DF	LRT		Variable class	Estimate (OR)	Loge	SE	Odds ratio
		DR	Pr>x ²					
Intercept		96.55	<.0001				0.2750	
District	1	0.88	0.3469	Fagita lekoma	-0.1507		0.1602	0.8601
				Banja	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Kebeles	9	7.80	0.0052	Fagita	-0.5058		0.1811	0.6030
		35.32	<.0001	Sigla dawuna	-0.9955		0.1675	0.3695
		0.07	0.7858	Furi jegola	0.051		0.1877	1.0523
		20.13	<.0001	Gafera	-0.7619		0.1698	0.4668
				Chiguali	0*		0.0000	1.0000
		0.37	0.5435	Asem selase	-0.0901		0.1484	0.9138
		13.53	0.0002	Dangia	-0.6545		0.1780	0.5197
		6.98	0.0082	Gagasta	0.3897		0.1475	1.4765
		0.57	0.4490	Gomerta	-0.1141		0.1507	0.8922
		Akena	0*		0.0000	1.0000		
Planting date	1	12.08	0.0005	May	-0.3082		0.0887	0.7348
				June	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Variety	5	45.14	<.0001	Key	1.2699		0.1890	3.5605
		35.74	<.0001	Abalo	1.1744		0.1965	3.2362
		57.94	<.0001	Zerngena	1.9725		0.2591	7.1886
		32.27	<.0001	Guassa	1.292		0.2275	3.6401
		11.97	0.0005	Gudene	0.6637		0.1919	1.9419
		Belete	0*		0.0000	1.0000		
Previous crop	4	4.30	0.0381	Potato	0.3074		0.1482	1.3599
		0.30	0.5810	Maize	-0.0719		0.1303	0.9306
		3.25	0.0715	Tef	-0.28		0.1554	0.7558
		13.24	0.0003	Wheat	-0.7084		0.1947	0.4924
		Barley	0*		0.0000	1.0000		
Cropping system	1	6.79	0.0092	Intercropping	-0.2656		0.1019	0.7667
				Sole cropping	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Growth stage	1	19.49	<.0001	Flowering	0.405		0.0918	1.4993
				Vegetative	0*		0.0000	1.0000
Fungicide used	1	260.98	<.0001	Untreated	1.8907		0.1170	6.6240
				Treated	0*		0.0000	1.0000

DF degrees of freedom, DR deviance reduction, LRT likelihood ratio test, Pr probability of a value χ^2 exceeding the deviance reduction, χ^2 chi-square value, *Reference group, OR odds ratio, SE standard error

CONCLUSION

Potato late blight was the main constraint that threatens potato production in subsistence farming, and was widely distributed over the surveyed area due to the availability of conducive environments. Late blight prevalence, incidence, and severities were highest in Banja district while the lowest were in Fagita Lekoma district. Biophysical factors like planting in the month of May, altitude <2300 mean above sea level, intercropping, previous crop with wheat, *Tef*, and maize, improved potato varieties used, vegetative crop growth stage, application of fungicides reduced potato late blight intensities across districts, and *Kebele* administrations. The majority of the potato fields were sole cropped, susceptible local varieties, rotated with cereal crops, and early planted. The sole cropping and susceptible varieties (*Key* and *Abalo*) in the surveyed fields resulting the epidemics of late blight of potato. Fields with fungicide management showed the lowest incidence and severity of late blight compared to other respective variable classes. The lowest probability of association was observed on May planted fields, previous crops with wheat and maize, and intercropping fields. Early planting, intercropping, and rotation with non-host

crops, use of improved potato varieties, and spray with novel fungicides were important variables to reduced late blight disease incidence and severity. Agroecology based integrated management options for the control potato late blight should be needed to increase the production and productivity of potato.

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